

Synthesis of 3-(2'-Methyl-4'-ethoxy-5'-isopropylphenyl)-4-aryl butyric Acids

R. P. Rao and R. A. Kulkarni

Nerurkar *et al.*¹ have synthesized various 3-aryl-4-aryl butyric acids by condensation of various phenolic ethers with β -aryl glutaric anhydrides. Adopting conditions similar to Chakravarti² various phenolic ethers have been condensed with 3-(2'-methyl-4'-ethoxy-5'-isopropylphenyl) glutaric anhydride to yield corresponding 3-aryl-4-aryl butyric acids of the type I. Formation of these acids was confirmed on the basis of their elemental analysis.

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To a solution of 3-(2'-methyl-4'-ethoxy-5'-isopropylphenyl) glutaric anhydride (0.01 mole) in 30 ml. of nitrobenzene and powdered anhydrous aluminium chloride, (2.25 mole), phenolic ether was added dropwise through a separating funnel. The content was kept stirring in a water bath at 45–50° for 6 hr. The content was cooled and decomposed with ice-cold hydrochloric acid. The heterogeneous mass was then subjected to steam distillation to remove nitrobenzene. The residue thus obtained was treated with sodium bicarbonate solution. The alkaline filtrate on acidification yielded the keto acid which was crystallised from dil. ethanol.

No.	R	Yield %	m.p. °C	Formula	Analysis				Derivative 2:4-DNP M.P. °C
					% Carbon Calc.	% Carbon Found	% Hydrogen Calc.	% Hydrogen Found	
1.	Anisole	55	180–81	C ₂₄ H ₃₀ O ₅	72.33	71.91	7.59	7.28	235–36
2.	Phenatole	45	177–78	C ₂₅ H ₃₂ O ₅	72.80	72.67	7.82	7.58	250–51
3.	<i>m</i> -Cresol methyl ether	50	175–76	C ₂₅ H ₃₂ O ₅	72.80	72.71	7.82	7.49	240–42
4.	<i>o</i> -Cresol methyl ether	72	179–80	C ₂₅ H ₃₂ O ₅	72.80	73.10	7.82	7.53	225–26
5.	<i>p</i> -Cresol methyl ether	57	176–77	C ₂₆ H ₃₂ O ₅	72.80	72.52	7.82	7.91	235–36
6.	β -Naphthyl methyl ether	60	184–85	C ₂₈ H ₃₂ O ₅	74.96	74.51	7.19	6.87	234–35
7.	α -Naphthyl methyl ether	60	175–76	C ₂₈ H ₃₂ O ₅	74.96	74.71	7.19	6.89	240–41
8.	Resorcinol dimethyl ether	40	183–84	C ₂₈ H ₃₂ O ₆	70.08	69.89	7.53	7.31	243–45
9.	Hydroquinone dimethyl ether	55	115–16	C ₂₅ H ₃₂ O ₆	70.08	69.72	7.53	7.19	196–97
10.	Orcinol dimethyl ether	70	175–76	C ₂₈ H ₃₄ O ₆	70.57	69.92	7.75	7.31	247–48
11.	Diphenyl Oxide	70	173–74	C ₂₉ H ₃₂ O ₆	75.60	75.32	7.00	6.81	250–51
12.	Thymol methyl ether	57	150–51	C ₂₈ H ₃₈ O ₅	73.96	73.52	8.42	7.91	238–39

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Department of Chemistry,
Ramnarian Ruia College,
Bombay-19.

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1. J. J. Nerurkar, R. N. Joshi, V. N. Maratho, G. S. Phadke and V. M. Bhave, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1960, **25**, 1491.
2. D. Chakravarti and N. K. Roy, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1965, **42**, 607.